

SMELL AND ITS EXPRESSION

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Annotation. This article talks about the concept of smell and its linguistic expression. Through the concept of smell, it serves the purpose of the writer to differentiate and highlight the characters according to different signs. Verbalization of the concept of smell through linguistic means in a literary text is considered.

Key words: concept, smell, odor, olfactory, representation, verbalization, linguistic means, differentiation, verbalization of the concept of smell.

The concept of "smell" is "a concept related to the sense of smell and which preserves knowledge about the olfactory properties of things and its linguistic expression in the human mind" [2, 3]. The conceptual component that is the core of the concept of "smell" is the content of the concept, which is formed from all "types" and general meaning symbols, from aromas to odors" [2, 9] " includes Smell, understood as a olfactory sign of objects of reality, is an integral part of the information that a person receives through the ability of sensory perception. The task of the concept of "smell" is to understand the olfactory properties of real objects and to express the received information through language units. Smell is one of the various signs of objects of reality that can be perceived by a person's sense of smell. In fact, the olfactory process is a human interaction with the material world. Interaction implies the existence of a connection between two or more elements, a relationship, which determines the situational nature of olfactory perception.

Conceptual analysis is a method of systematization of knowledge or information stored in the human mind and obtained through semantic analysis of language units. A concept is a data model related to a certain event, object, etc., existing in objective reality. The concept should include all knowledge about the indicated phenomenon. The parts that make up the content of the concept of linguistic research are: conceptual, figurative, evaluative, emotional, ethno-cultural, cultural, associative, etc. It is these components that cover the informative content of the concept. This, in turn, forms the structure of the concept. An important feature of the concept is its ability to enter into certain connections and relationships with other phenomena.

It seems that it is necessary to distinguish between the lexical concept of "smell" and the syntactic concept of "smell". In the first case, the

meaningful side of the concept is formed by smell as a real world phenomenon that reflects the olfactory properties of objects of reality. In the second case, the content of the concept has its own participants and the relationship between them, which ultimately leads to the process of smell perception. Verbalization of the concept of olfactory perception is carried out using syntactic means - block diagrams of various types of sentences. Note that if we understand a frame as "a structure of knowledge organized in the form of a representation of a stereotyped situation" [5, 10] and take into account that it is a "linguistic analogue of a frame", this concept can be considered a frame. An invariant semantic structure is a proposition that can have different forms" [3, 3]. The means of indicating an olfactory situation is a linguistic sentence in which the participants of an olfactory situation find expression. The elements of the olfactory state are:

- 1) smell or attribute of smell;
- 2) the receptor or subject of perception (it should be noted that the perceiver can be implied);
- 3) source of smell - an object of the physical world that is the carrier of the attribute of smell.

The colloquial analysis of the concept of "smell" in the text of the work of art allows for a more detailed description of the content of this concept. The perceptual concept of "smell" in the literary text serves the purpose of describing a certain fragment of reality in the text. The phenomenon of smell is closely related to the objective world. The manifestation of this connection is that giving the concept of "smell" in the text implies the actualization of the aspects of reality related to the phenomenon of smell.

The concept of "smell" serves to express in language the most important signs of the surrounding reality. The olfactory property allows the use of smell-representative units as a special code by connecting them with various elements of reality. "Both physical objects, abstract concepts, and emotions fall into the acoustic-visual images of the mind, which define the object and act as symbols with a certain meaning" [1, 164]. The connection of "smell" with other concepts is highlighted in a unique way in the text of the artistic work.

In the artistic text, olfactory means indicate the state of smell perception. It is a symbol representing events and situations. In the literary text, the units representing smell serve to reveal the informative content of the sentence. The basis of such activity is the mechanism of associative connection. "A person has words with a conditionally stable meaning in the primary denomination, and in

the secondary denomination, semantic connotations arise as a result of the associative activity of the mind that connects this sign with various elements of reality" [4, 110]. The associative activity of the mind discussed in this quote works with the linguistic symbols that comprise the sentence. A sentence, like a word, can have additional, associatively determined shades of meaning. Unlike words, these are not figurative meanings, but stereotypical images of a symbolic nature. In the novel "Horizon" by S. Akhmad, the sentences indicating the olfactory state perform several functions. They are based on the fact that the smell is meaningfully connected with things and events of the real world, and that it is "buried" in objective reality. It should be noted that the linguistic functions of smell are also determined by the uniqueness of the text of the work, the use of the phenomenon of smell according to the author's purpose. Scent is used along with other tools to create the perfect image. In the text of the novel, the concept of "smell" is found in certain typical passages. Often, the author refers to various olfactory images.

When describing the early morning, the writer describes the heat of the bread spreading from the courtyards. This fact can be explained in an extralinguistic way: this situation corresponds to the lifestyle of the period being described - bread was baked in the morning in almost all households.

Therefore, the analysis of the meaningful side of language units that objectify the concept of "smell" shows that the concept of "smell" is related to the fields of concepts of man, nature, space, and time, which include more specific concepts of profession. Type of activity, social status, time of day, season, natural phenomena, residence / non-residence, cooking, daily life, past tense, antiquity, etc. The associative relationship of the concept of "smell" with other concepts is realized in different ways in the text. Olfactory units are used as a means of portrait characterization, landscape description, indicators of social status, belonging to a certain culture, etc. As a powerful figurative and expressive tool, they affect the emotions and enhance the impression of what is read.

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